

TARGET INGREDIENTS FOR MODIFYING THE PROPERTIES OF POLYMER SOLE COMPOSITIONS

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Annotation : The article investigates modifying additives to control the values of physicochemical and physico-mechanical properties of composite materials obtained on the basis of elastomer and thermoplastic mixtures for the bottom of shoes.

Keywords : increasing heat and light resistance, resistance to thermal aging, gasoline and oil resistance, frost resistance of composite materials, stabilizers, softeners, plasticizers, fillers.

ЦЕЛЕВЫЕ ИНГРЕДИЕНТЫ ДЛЯ МОДИФИКАЦИИ СВОЙСТВ ПОЛИМЕРНО ПОДОШВЕННЫХ КОМПОЗИЦИЙ

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Аннотация: В этой статье исследованы модифицирующие добавки для регулирования значений физико-химических и физико-механических свойств композиционных материалов, полученных на основе эластомерных и термопластичных смесей для низа обуви.

Ключевые слова: повышения тепло- и светостойкости, устойчивости к тепловому старению, бензо-, маслостойкость, морозостойкость

КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ, СТАБИЛИЗАТОРЫ, МЯГЧИТЕЛИ, ПЛАСТИФИКАТОРЫ, НАПОЛНИТЕЛИ.

In order to regulate the values of physicochemical and physico-mechanical properties, as well as to increase heat and light resistance, resistance to thermal aging, gasoline, oil and frost resistance of composite materials obtained on the basis of mixtures of elastomer and thermoplastic, as modifying additives are introduced various stabilizers, softeners, plasticizers and fillers. For this purpose, low molecular weight substances of various nature are used.

Fillers are used to improve the performance properties of compositions, give them various specific properties and reduce the cost of the material. The introduction of fillers also regulate the technological properties of compositions and facilitate their processing into products [1,2].

Filling is one of the main ways to create polymer compositions with specified technological and operational characteristics. Depending on the nature of the interaction with the polymer, fillers are conditionally divided into inert (does not change the properties of the composition) and active (strengthening the composition due to interaction with the base polymer), and by their nature - into organic and inorganic.

Active fillers include carbon black (soot), highly dispersed silicic acid (white soot), as well as zinc and magnesium oxides, magnesium and calcium silicates, and lignin. However, most fillers are inert. As a rule, they have a low cost. Their introduction into the composition can even slightly worsen the mechanical properties, but significantly reduce its cost, as well as impart new specific properties to the composition. For example, graphite powder or molybdenum disulfide is added to polymers to impart antifriction properties.

The content of fillers in polymer compositions can vary over a wide range and, based on the total weight of the composition, is usually 15-50%. However, there are highly filled compositions in which the concentration of the filler can exceed the content of the polymer itself by several times.

Plasticizers are introduced into the base polymer in order to impart (or increase) plasticity during the processing of the polymer composition and elasticity during the operation of products. Plasticization, being a physical modification of the polymer, lowers the processing temperature of the composition, facilitates its molding, increases the frost resistance of the material, and reduces the value of the elasticity modulus. The introduction of plasticizers into the composition facilitates the mixing of the polymer with other components, and in some cases imparts such valuable properties as incombustibility, thermal and light resistance. However, the main

purpose of the introduction of plasticizers is to increase the elasticity of the polymer composition during the operation of products [2–5].

Organic low-molecular, oligomeric or high-molecular compounds are used as plasticizers. According to the state of aggregation, they can be both liquid and solid. Plasticizers are subject to the following requirements:

- the ability to combine with the polymer to form a system with operational stability;
- low volatility;
- colorless, no smell;
- preservation of the plasticizing action at the lowest operating temperatures;
- chemical resistance, no less than that of the base polymer.

Stabilizers. During processing, operation and storage, polymers and compositions based on them are exposed to heat, oxygen, light, moisture, penetrating radiation, aggressive chemical media, biological agents, mechanical stresses, etc. As a result, aging of polymers occurs, which is expressed in change in physical, mechanical and other properties of a material or product. The main role during aging is played by chemical transformations of molecular chains and, first of all, by the destruction and crosslinking of macromolecules [4].

To increase the stability of polymeric materials, they are stabilized by introducing special additives - stabilizers into the compositions.

By functional purpose, stabilizers are divided into antioxidants, antiozonants, light stabilizers, antirads, heat stabilizers, biochemical and antifatigue.

Vulcanizing systems are substances used to vulcanize a rubber compound. They regulate the crosslinking of rubber macromolecules into a three-dimensional structure during the vulcanization process. These include vulcanizing agents, accelerators, activators, and scorch retarders (anticorching) [6,7].

Vulcanizing agents are ingredients of rubber compounds that ensure the vulcanization reaction proceeds. Sulfur remains the most common vulcanizing agent to date. Metal oxides (ZnO, MgO, PbO, CaO), organic peroxides, organic di- and polysulfides, phenol-formaldehyde oligomers, diamines, and diisocyanates are also used as vulcanizing agents. Magnesium and zinc oxides are used in the vulcanization of chloroprene and carboxylate rubbers. Organic peroxides are used in the vulcanization of siloxane, ethylene-propylene and fluorine-containing rubbers, as well as ethylene-vinyl acetate copolymers.

Vulcanization accelerators are substances added to the rubber compound to speed up the vulcanization process. Thus, the vulcanization of natural rubber with sulfur without accelerators at 140 °C takes 3-4 hours, and in the presence of accelerators - in a few minutes. The type of accelerator and its concentration, in

addition to influencing the kinetics of vulcanization, have a significant effect on the physical and mechanical properties of vulcanizates and the nature of their change during aging. The increase in the rate of cross-linking of rubber macromolecules in the presence of accelerators is due to the fact that they increase the reactivity of vulcanizing agents, and the improvement in physical and mechanical properties is due to the influence of accelerators on the nature of the chemical bonds formed between macromolecules.

As vulcanization accelerators, organic compounds are mainly used - thiazoles, sulfenamides, guanidines, dithiocarbamates, thiurams, xanthates. Most rubber compounds contain two or even three types of accelerators.

Vulcanization activators increase the efficiency of accelerators. The main function of activators is to increase the frequency of the vulcanization mesh. The main vulcanization activators are oxides of zinc, magnesium, lead, strontium, cadmium, bismuth, and combinations thereof.

Scorch retarders (anticorching) are components of rubber compounds that prevent their premature vulcanization and allow increasing the duration of the mixtures in a viscous state during their technological processing. However, anti-scorching should not slow down the vulcanization process.

The most effective scorch retarders are organic acids and their anhydrides (phthalic anhydride is the most commonly used).

Hardeners. Hardeners are components that cause curing of reactive oligomers, as a result of which the oligomers are irreversibly converted into solid, insoluble and infusible three-dimensional polymers [8-10].

According to the nature of the action, hardeners are divided into the following groups:

the hardeners themselves, the molecules of which react with the functional groups of oligomers and enter the structure of the resulting polymers;

curing initiators and catalysts.

Special additives. Special-purpose ingredients include substances with a specific action: blowing agents, modifiers, structure formers, odorants, flame retardants, anti-static agents, dispersants, dyes, lubricants [11,12].

Secondary compositions include technological waste and products that were in operation.

Technological waste is extrusion, sprues, defective products, samples subjected to testing, products obtained during the adjustment of processing equipment. Technological waste is subjected to crushing to the size of granules or, conversely, granulation, after which it is added to the composition in an amount of 5-15% of the feedstock.

The regenerate is a product of the processing of waste rubber production, as well as rubber products that were in use, but capable of re-vulcanization. The introduction of the regenerate into the rubber compound facilitates the mixing process, while the regenerate acts as a dispersant and softener and improves some properties of the vulcanizate. The amount of regenerate in rubber compounds ranges from 10 to 500% of the mass of rubber, depending on the type of regenerate and the requirements for the vulcanizate. In rubber compounds for bottom parts of shoes, the regenerate content does not exceed 20% of the rubber mass [13, 14].

In addition to the regenerate, rubber flour is often added to rubber mixtures, which is made by grinding technological waste from the production of rubber products. Unlike crushed waste of thermoplastic materials, rubber flour is a powder with a particle size of not more than 0.9 mm. In the manufacture of rubber flour, the treated waste is crushed on rollers, and then crushed in disc or plate mills.

Rubber flour, in fact, is an inert powdered filler and is added to the mixture in an amount of up to 5-7% of the rubber mass in order to reduce the cost of the mixture.

Thus, polymeric compositions may contain various kinds of target ingredients, i.e., polymeric and non-polymeric components that perform different functions. At the same time, many ingredients perform a double or even triple function. At the same time, to increase the effectiveness of the action, two or even several ingredients with the same functional purpose are introduced into the compositions.

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